

ARGOS

Conceptual Design Study

Designing a Next-Generation Radio Facility for Multi-Messenger Astronomy

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Disclaimer

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Applicable documents

In the event of conflict between the contents of the following documents and this document, the following documents shall take precedence.

1. ARGOS-CDS Grant Agreement (no 101094354):
ARGOS_Grant_Agreement_101094354_v1.pdf

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1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and scope of this document

The purpose of this document is to provide a design overview and status update of the ARGOS Signal-Processing subsystem. This subsystem can roughly be broken into four independent pipelines. Here we provide a summary of the logical and physical design of each pipeline, as well as any results obtained at the time of writing. This document also provides the global integration and deployment plan for all of the pipelines.

This document does not focus on the scientific applications of the ARGOS project, which are detailed in *D2.1: ARGOS Level 0 Science Requirements* but rather on the pipelines under development to deliver science-ready products.

1.2 Document structure

This document is structured as follows. The following of this section presents ARGOS and remind the mission, stakeholders, and uses cases. Section 2 presents the logical breakdown of the signal processing subsystem. Section 3 provides a global description of the physical design of the specific pipelines that will be developed for the ARGOS project. Section 4 lists the level-1 requirements for the Signal-Processing subsystem and how these relate to the global level-0 requirements of ARGOS. Section 5 describes the architecture of the subsystem and how it interfaces with other ARGOS (sub)systems. Section 6 presents the results obtained so far and the future development plans. Finally, some concluding remarks are given in Sect. 7.

1.3 Related documents

- 1.1. ARGOS-CDS Grant Agreement (no 101094354):
ARGOS_Grant_Agreement_101094354_v1.pdf
- 1.2. D2.1: ARGOS Level 0 Science Requirements
- 1.3. D6.2: Backend Subsystem Design

1.4 Full ARGOS array vs pathfinder

The majority of the pipelines should run (more or less) in the same way for the full ARGOS array and the ARGOS pathfinder array. That said, the computational bandwidth, as well as the quality of output products may differ significantly between the two cases. Therefore, unless otherwise stated, the information provided in this document can be considered to be primarily relevant for the full ARGOS array. All references to “ARGOS” are to the full array, while any points relevant to the ‘pathfinder’ or ‘conceptual design study’ refer specifically to the initial ARGOS pathfinder array.

1.5 Mission

The Signal-Processing subsystem (SPS; also referred to as the science processor) can be considered as a logical component of the ARGOS telescope. The purpose of the subsystem is to consume the beamformer and correlator outputs and process them to create science-ready datasets, with minimal human intervention. More specifically, the scope of WP7 is to design and implement three independent science pipelines:

- An *image reconstruction pipeline* that will be processing the correlator output to produce flux- and polarisation-calibrated images, as well as astrometric solutions, source catalogues, classifications and alerts for outstanding events.
- A *pulsar timing pipeline* that will be processing the beamformed timeseries to produce pulsar timing products such as flux- and polarisation-calibrated, coherently de-dispersed pulse profiles, dynamic spectra and pulse times-of-arrival (TOAs), as well as timing solutions and alerts for outlier events (e.g. pulse profile changes, strong scattering events and glitches).
- A commensal *fast transient pipeline* to monitor the beamformer output for astrophysical transients such as fast radio bursts (FRBs) and produce alerts and detection information (e.g. astrometry, flux- and polarisation- burst profiles etc.).

In addition, WP7 shall implement a calibration pipeline to calculate and monitor the complex antenna gains.

1.6 Stakeholders

The SPS will be interfacing with the telescope control system, the digital backend, as well as the archiving and alerts subsystem. The following key stakeholders have been identified.

Telescope operators: That is, the people managing the telescope. Telescope operators may interact with the SPS either directly (i.e., to manually run a specific pipeline and monitor its output) or indirectly (i.e., via the backend or the archive, to monitor the health of the telescope and the quality of its output).

Developers: the team responsible for developing and maintaining the SPS software, as well as the broader developer community that may want to clone and/or repurpose part of the SPS software for another application.

DevOps and system administrators: the people responsible for deploying and monitoring the SPS software on the ARGOS high performance computing (HPC) infrastructure.

Backend engineers: the team(s) responsible for developing and operating the digital backend.

Scientists: the people that want to retrieve a science data set from the archive or to be notified for an interesting astrophysical event identified by the telescope.

1.7 Use Cases

Here, we describe four use cases (user stories) that require action from the SPS and capture some major requirements for the scientists and telescope operators. Additional examples are shown in Figure 1 and can also be found in section 4 of *D6.2: Backend Subsystem Design*.

6. Step 4 is repeated for the imaging observation using the updated gain solutions.
7. The SPS imaging module performs radio frequency interference (RFI) excision and processes the visibilities and produces an image.
8. The SPS processes the image cube and extracts source information.
9. The SPS performs astrometric calibration.
10. The SPS inserts the detected sources to the ARGOS source catalogue.
11. The SPS performs classification, flags new and/or variable sources and transmits alerts if needed.
12. The SPS stores the image and related metadata (diagnostic plots etc.) in the archive and deletes the raw data.

Use case 3: Retrieval of a pulsar timing dataset

1. The SPS receives a request from the Archive subsystem to produce a new timing.
2. The SPS retrieves the required dataset from the Archive.
3. The SPS produces a new timing solution.
4. The new timing solution is transmitted to the archive and is downloaded by the user.

Use case 4: Detection of a fast radio burst

1. The SPS retrieves the commensal beamformed timeseries produced by the backend.
2. The SPS produces de-dispersed timeseries for the predefined trial dispersion measures.
3. The SPS searches the resulting timeseries for bursts.
4. The SPS detects a burst.
5. The SPS triggers a data dump.
6. The burst data (filterbank file containing the Stokes timeseries and metadata for the burst) and diagnostic plots are passed to the Archive subsystem for storage.
7. The SPS generates an alert and transmits it to the Archive subsystem.

2 Logical Breakdown of the Signal Processing Subsystem

The Signal-Processing subsystem is tasked with providing state-of-the-art processing and machine learning tools for the reduction of raw ARGOS data, in the form of various data analysis pipelines. The primary objective is to provide science-ready data products to ARGOS members and the wider community. The subsystem designed and implemented in the context of the ARGOS conceptual design study (CDS), consists of the logical components shown in Figure 2 (management, calibration, transient search, imaging and pulsar timing).

Additional logical components covering extended use cases may be developed at a later stage. A general plan for each of these pipelines is provided in the following sections. Here, we describe the various logical components and their functions.

Figure 2: SPS logical components.

2.1 Management

The management component is responsible for:

- Interfacing with the telescope control system, the backend and the archive,
- monitoring the other SPS components,
- provisioning resources for the other SPS components.

2.2 Calibration

Figure 3: Logical components of the calibration module.

The logical breakdown of the calibration component is shown in Figure 3. The calibration scheme chosen for ARGOS follows standard interferometric calibration practices, such as the ones used for the VLA and MeerKAT telescopes. However, the large field-of-view of the array in many cases requires some extra specialized calibration steps.

Delays: A Priori Delay calibration: The delays component is responsible for calculating coarse delays (geometric + instrumental) as a function of polarisation and frequency, to initialise the digitizers. At the start of each observing cycle the backend shall use the most recent available delay calibration solution to initialise the complex gains for each antenna. As a next step, short (few min) observation of a bright, well characterised source shall be used to iteratively refine the antenna-based delays. Lastly, the phase and cross-polarisation delays shall be refined using brief observations of the frontend noise diodes.

Catalogue: The catalogue component is responsible for maintaining an up-to-date list of calibrators and their properties. The calibrators should be bright enough to be detected by individual antennas within a few minutes of observations. One potential significant challenge given the large FoV and sensitivity of the array is cross contamination by secondary sources inside the calibrator fields. To compensate for such affects detailed models of the main ARGOS calibrator fields should be constructed using sensitive, high-resolution observations with other interferometers or with the EVN.

Phase calibration: In addition to the calibration cycles described above, the phase solutions shall be refined using higher-cadence monitoring of a suitable set of phase calibrators. Given the large FoV of the array, suitable phase calibrators will be available inside most science fields. These could be either bright continuum sources or pulsars. The calibration pipeline shall make use of these sources to refine the phase calibration ‘on the fly’ and with a relatively high cadence, for instance on timescales shorter than 30 minutes. These solutions will provide updates to the antenna gains that will be made available to the backend, also on the fly, at the start of each subsequent science run. To achieve this calibration step, a catalogue of calibration sources with a density of at least ~ 1 per 10 deg^2 shall be compiled. As above, contamination from secondary sources in the field may be challenging to overcome and therefore priority will be placed on implementing a phase calibration scheme that makes use of gated pulsar observations and/or making use of the noise diodes fired at pre-defined time patterns.

Astrometric calibration: To obtain accurate measurements of celestial objects, it is important to evaluate and mitigate various sources of errors and offsets from local, close field, and far fields. Common atmospheric contributors include the troposphere and ionosphere. Tropospheric delay is mostly frequency-independent and primarily caused by moisture in clouds. The ‘phase referencing’ method is a well-established standard for calibrating this effect, involving simultaneous observations of two closely spaced sources, with one serving as a calibrator. The calibrator’s phase is used to correct the target’s phase. Although finding calibrators close enough for ‘in-beam’ calibration can be challenging, the large field of view of ARGOS facilitates this task. Ionospheric delay is usually frequency-dependent; thus, multi-frequency or ultra-wideband observations are preferable, and data on the vertical total electron content from the Global Positioning System can be beneficial. Local contributors to delays, such as clock errors in instruments, can be calibrated using ‘geodetic blocks’, and antenna positions can be measured using Earth’s Orientation Parameters. Far-field contributors, like the structure of the source, can be mitigated by calibrating visibilities using bright calibrators with techniques like closure relationships.

Archive: The archive component is responsible for storing the calibration solutions, as well as any available models for the calibrator fields.

Flux calibration: Similarly, observations of a few carefully chosen flux calibrators shall be performed to scale the complex antenna gains to absolute flux density units and to calibrate the bandpass. Flux calibration must also require accurate source models for the sources to minimize the introduction of artifacts in the bandpass. The cadence of the delay and bandpass calibration observations shall be chosen based on the scientific application. However, to ensure compliance with the ARGOS science requirements, it is recommended that a complete delay and flux calibration cycle is scheduled at least once every 4-6 hours.

Polarisation calibration: The ARGOS antennas are equipped with orthogonal linear polarisation feeds. While the noise diodes can be used to calibrate the absolute polarisation angle, certain use cases that require higher dynamic range shall also make use of astronomical sources for calibration. The polarisation calibration logical component is responsible for providing absolute polarimetric calibration. A strong unpolarised source shall be observed at least once per day to calculate the so-called leakage terms which add a fraction of the Stokes I to the cross-hand polarisation terms. The absolute polarisation angle shall be calibrated with a well-characterised source such as 3C 286. Additional, higher-cadence polarisation calibration shall also be performed as part of other logical components, such as the pulsar timing module.

2.3 Pulsar Timing

This component is responsible for processing the coherently beamformed timeseries of the backend to produce pulsar timing products. The associated tasks can be broken down into several logical components, as can be seen in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Pulsar timing logical component.

RFI excision: The RFI excision logical component performs radio-frequency interference excision on the beamformed timeseries. It also provides additional RFI excision function.

Folding: The folding logical component uses a stored pulsar ephemeris to map the timestamps of the de-dispersed timeseries to pulsar rotational phases, and to produce time-integrated average pulsar profiles, as well as diagnostic plots (e.g. waterfall diagrams).

Coherent de-dispersion: This logical component performs coherent de-dispersion of the full Stokes phased-array beams to undo cold-plasma-induced frequency dispersion from signal propagation through the interstellar medium.

Polarisation and flux calibration: Pulsars can be strongly polarised sources and therefore many science applications require careful calibration, in particular of the cross-coupling terms of the polarisation response that are typically discarded in standard calibration procedures (under the ‘ideal feed assumption’). These logical components perform complementary polarisation and flux calibration using appropriate time-series data of ‘standard-candle’ pulsars to determine the receptor orientation and ellipticity terms of the polarimetric response.

Times of Arrival estimation: This component cross-correlates the pulsar profiles with templates and/or reference high signal-to-noise profiles to measure times of arrival (TOAs), as well as diagnostic plots.

Timing: The timing component uses the up-to-date set of TOAs to refine the timing solution.

Dynamic Spectra: The dynamic spectra logical component is responsible for analysing the de-dispersed pulsar templates, to produce dynamic spectra, secondary spectra and diagnostic plots for human investigation.

Database: The database is responsible for managing all secondary files and data products required for data reduction, namely:

- Timing ephemerides (i.e. the model that predicts the TOAs of a particular pulsar) used for de-dispersion and folding,
- Regularly updated timing ephemerides intended for science use,
- 1D and 2D template profiles used for TOA measurements,
- RFI excision masks,
- Müller matrixes for polarisation calibration,
- Clock correction files required for barycentric timing solutions,
- Information for flux calibration standards,
- Metadata in the form of .par file flags,
- Diagnostic plots such as pulsar residual plots, waterfall plots, dynamic spectra, etc.

Outliers and transient detection: This component performs a series of analyses on the final pulsar-timing products to flag bad-data outliers and detect transients such as:

- *Pulse profile variability* – using the folded profiles,
- *Extreme scattering events* – using the timing solution and secondary spectra,
- *Polarisation variability* – using the folded profiles,
- *Rotational glitches* – using the residuals of the timing solution,
- *Timing variability* – using the residuals of the timing solution.

2.4 Imaging

This pipeline will deliver 2D and 3D (2D + time) images derived from ARGOS visibilities. The imaging pipeline will employ both traditional image processing tools, such as sparse regularisation, as well as cutting-

edge machine learning architectures. The associated tasks can be broken down into several logical components, as can be seen in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Imaging timing logical component.

Source detection: This component will be in charge of identifying sources in the reconstructed images.

Transient detection: This component will deliver trained neural networks to classify the detected time varying radio-sources based on their flux, temporal evolution, spectral and polarisation properties. The networks will be trained using ARGOS simulations. This will be of significant interest for multi-messenger astronomy. The network will aim to classify transient sources (e.g. GW counterparts, radio supernovae, GRBs and FRBs), and eventually could be used to trigger follow-up observations for in-depth scientific analysis.

Astrometry: This component will provide astrometry of the detected source and transient. For example, it will provide the position of the object.

RFI excision: The RFI excision logical component performs radio-frequency interference excision on the de-dispersed timeseries.

Image reconstruction: This component will provide reconstructed images from visibilities. Several methods can be used and some are described in Sections 2.4.1 and 2.4.2. The application for ARGOS is described in Section 2.4.3.

Database: The database is responsible for managing all secondary files and data products required for data reduction, namely:

- Metadata of the antennas and observation parameters,
- Visibilities,
- Primary beam
- PSF of the observation (include the primary beam, but also the effect linked to the observation),
- Clean observation.

2.4.1 Traditional image processing methods

For any given baseline configuration, radio interferometers can only observe a limited number of visibilities (i.e. the Fourier space is not completely sampled). Therefore, proximal optimisation algorithms can be employed using 2D wavelets and a sparsity prior to accurately recover high-resolution pixel space images. This approach has been demonstrated to be highly effective and to outperform more traditional image reconstruction tools, such as CLEAN (Garsden, et al. 2015). This methodology can be extended to 3D by employing 2D-1D wavelet decomposition (see Figure 6), which is a tensorial product of 2D (spatial information) and 1D (temporal information) wavelet functions.

Figure 6: Schematic representation of the 2D-1D wavelet decomposition.

This 2D-1D approach can also be used to detect transient sources by comparing wavelet coefficients at different times. This functionality will either remain part of the image reconstruction pipeline or could be turned into a stand-alone pipeline for transient classification depending on the results and scientific needs.

2.4.2 Machine learning methods

Various machine learning architectures will also be explored as alternative means of reconstructing the pixel-based images from the ARGOS visibilities. Once trained on suitably representative sample of data, these networks have the potential to be significantly faster than iterative approaches and have more flexibility in adapting the solutions. These methods will build upon the work of e.g. (Sureau, Lechat and Starck 2020), (Nammour, et al. 2022), (Ramzi, et al. 2021), and in particular (Chiche, et al. 2023).

(Chiche, et al. 2023) introduced two novel machine learning architectures for reconstructing 3D (2D spatial + 1D temporal) radio imaging data and identify transient sources. The first implementation is a 2D-1D Net (see Figure 7), where, given a set of dirty images and corresponding point spread functions (PSFs), a set of features maps are extracted using a 2D network. These maps are stacked in the temporal dimensions and a follow-up 1D network is used to reconstruct the point source data cube. Correlation in the temporal

dimension help to identify transient sources that can be easily missed by an independent frame-by-frame reconstruction using e.g. CLEAN.

The second implementation is the so-called Deflation Net (see Figure 8), which works in a very similar fashion to the 2D-1D Net with the added step of subtracting the average sky model from the individual images. This effectively removes all constant sources and allows more efficient reconstruction and detection of transient sources.

Either or both of these architectures could be integrated into the imaging pipeline. Alternatively, a new architecture building upon this work could be used. The final choice will be made following tests on simulated ARGOS data. The quality of the recovered image as well as computational coast will be taken into account.

Figure 7: 2D-1D Net architecture from (Chiche, et al. 2023).

Figure 8: Deflation Net architecture from (Chiche, et al. 2023).

2.4.3 Application to the ARGOS pathfinder

The current plan for the ARGOS pathfinder will be to have a fully functioning 2D image reconstruction pipeline in place that will implement CLEAN (as a baseline for comparison) along with a sparse and/or machine learning approach. The remaining 2D and 3D tools will likely be tested on the ARGOS pathfinder data, but the results are not expected to be highly competitive at this scale. The main initial results for these methods will come from simulations of the full or pathfinder ARGOS array.

The `argosim`¹ Python package has been specifically developed as part of the WP7. The aim of the package is to test different image reconstruction pipeline for ARGOS. It currently allows users to choose an array configuration, simulate a radio image, and reconstruct the image using the CLEAN algorithm. Multiple modules have been implemented for selecting different array setups, including circular, Y-shape, random, and regular grid configurations. From the chosen array configuration, the baselines for a source at a given position (declination and hour angle) can be calculated, based on the array's geographic location (latitude and longitude). By specifying the observation frequencies and tracking time, the package allow to compute the corresponding uv-plane.

For simulating radio images, the sky is modelled with a given FoV, size (number of pixels), and source sizes. The simulations provide sampled visibilities on which a Gaussian noise is added. Additionally, the primary beam of the antennas is accounted for, based on simulations provided by WP5.

Finally, the Högbom's CLEAN algorithm (Högbom 1974) is applied to these simulated visibilities to reconstruct the image. We can control the number of iterations and threshold used in the CLEAN algorithm. A clean beam, modelled by a Gaussian with a full width at half maximum (FWHM) similar to the size of the real beam, is employed to produce clean and reconstructed images.

In the future, we plan to incorporate additional sources of noise and enhance our sky model for more realistic simulations. We also aim to implement alternative image reconstruction methods (such as those mentioned previously) to evaluate their efficiency and computational cost. In particular, we are planning to investigate how each implementation scales and how can then be used in practice for ARGOS (given the fact that visibilities will not be stored for long time).

2.5 Transient Search

Figure 9: Transient logical component.

The transient search pipeline is responsible for detecting and analysing short-duration radio transients—such as those produced by pulsars, fast radio bursts (FRBs), and magnetars—in ARGOS coherent and incoherent

¹ <https://github.com/ARGOS-telescope/argosim>

beam data. It employs large memory buffers that temporarily store antenna voltage data. Upon detection of a candidate signal, a snapshot of the relevant portion of the buffer is written to disk for further analysis.

The recorded voltages are coherently dedispersed and full-Stokes detected to derive the polarisation properties of the candidate. These voltages are also sent to a separate offline correlator to generate interferometric images, enabling precise source localisation. Time-domain data, images, and derived parameters (e.g. polarisation and position) are transmitted to the archiving subsystem, where public alerts may be generated.

The pipeline is structured into three main stages:

1. Candidate detection and classification
2. Voltage buffer triggering and recording
3. Parameter estimation

Each stage is described in detail below.

2.5.1 Candidate Detection and Classification

Figure 10: Candidate detection and classification logical component.

The transient search pipeline receives total power data that is both time- and frequency-resolved. To determine the presence of a transient signal, the following logical processing steps are applied:

RFI excision: Radio-frequency interference (RFI) is removed from the data through a combination of narrow- and wide-band identification techniques. Detected RFI is either excised or replaced to minimize contamination of subsequent analysis steps.

Incoherent de-dispersion: A defining characteristic of astrophysical transients is the frequency-dependent delay introduced by their propagation through ionized media. Since the true dispersion measure (DM) is unknown a priori, the data must be searched across a range of trial DMs. Incoherent dedispersion corrects for this dispersion by applying time shifts to each frequency channel and integrating the result to form a single-channel time series for each DM trial.

Matched filtering: As the time-domain profile of a transient is not known in advance, matched filtering is used to increase the likelihood of detection. Boxcar filters of varying widths are applied to each dedispersed time series to capture signals with different durations. Filtered time series are then thresholded, and those exceeding a defined significance level are retained as candidate detections.

Candidate clustering: Since a real transient may be detected across multiple nearby DM trials, clustering is performed to group related detections and reduce duplication. This step outputs a list of candidate clusters, each representing a unique transient detection along with its associated properties.

Diagnostic generation: For each candidate cluster, a diagnostic file is generated to support classification. This includes extracted time windows from the beamformed total power data, dedispersed time series, and metadata describing the candidate's properties.

Candidate classification: Diagnostic data are fed into a machine learning classifier, which assesses the likelihood that each candidate is astrophysical. Candidates deemed high-probability and not associated with known sources (unless explicitly permitted) trigger alerts that initiate voltage buffer recording.

2.5.2 Voltage Recording

When a high-quality candidate is identified, an internal alert is passed to the voltage buffering system. Using the candidate's timestamp, reference frequency, and dispersion measure, a time window within the buffer is selected for extraction. This window is frequency-dependent and typically spans only a few tens of milliseconds around the time of the candidate event. The corresponding voltages are saved to disk for detailed analysis.

2.5.3 Detailed Analysis

The stored voltages allow for more comprehensive time-domain and image-domain analyses. These analyses are interdependent and may require iteration to optimise the final results.

2.5.3.1 *Time domain analysis*

This analysis aims to refine the candidate's dispersion measure, extract a polarised light curve, and measure the rotation measure (RM), which quantifies the Faraday rotation experienced during propagation through cosmic magnetic fields. The following steps are applied:

Dedispersion optimisation: The buffered voltage data, which is frequency-resolved from the ARGOS F-engines, is subjected to both coherent and incoherent dedispersion over a refined range of DMs. Coherent dedispersion applies a quadratic phase correction to the voltages, allowing the dispersion effect to be fully removed. The optimal DM is selected based on criteria such as signal-to-noise ratio and the sharpness of the resulting light curve.

Stokes detection: Once the optimal DM is determined, the voltages are coherently dedispersed to this value and used to compute the Stokes parameters. This step requires a polarisation calibration solution from the imaging pipeline, which provides the Jones matrices necessary to correct the voltages for instrumental effects.

Rotation measure optimisation: With the full-Stokes data, RM synthesis is performed to estimate the candidate's rotation measure. This involves searching for a peak in linear polarisation intensity as a function of Faraday depth, indicating the most likely RM.

2.5.3.2 *Image domain analysis*

The goal of this stage is to determine the precise sky position of the candidate using interferometric imaging techniques adapted for the short durations involved.

Correlation: As with the normal backend processing, the recorded voltages will undergo correlation. Unlike the backend processing the voltages are first coherently dedispersed to the optimal dispersion measure.

Difference imaging: Given the short duration of the visibility data (on the order of tens of milliseconds), conventional image cleaning methods are ineffective. Instead, localization is achieved by differencing dirty images generated from on-pulse and off-pulse time windows. Since the dirty beam remains stable over such short intervals, this technique produces an unbiased and accurate position estimate. This method has proven effective with other interferometric arrays, such as MeerKAT and ASKAP.

If the derived position differs significantly from the initial beam center, it may be fed back into the time-domain analysis to re-beamform the data for improved results.

Following both time- and image-domain analyses, a final classification step removes false positives. Candidates that remain compelling are sent to the archiving subsystem, where public alerts may be generated and distributed.

3 Physical Design

A high-level overview of the functional-to-physical mapping for the SPS is shown in Figure 12. In this proposed design, the entire SPS is implemented on a COTS HPC cluster. The same cluster also hosts the Archive and Alerts subsystem, and part of the backend subsystem. The *management nodes* provide the resources required for managing, monitoring and operating the system. They provision load balancers for the

services that implement the processing logical components. Along with the *Ethernet network*, they also offer high-speed connection to storage.

Figure 12: Physical breakdown of the SPS.

The *processing nodes* provide the CPU and GPU processing capability required for the implementation of all logical functions, as well as high-speed network interfaces to management and storage nodes. Finally, a number of *storage nodes* provision the storage required to implement the storage logical functions.

3.1 Physical design of the calibration pipeline

Implementation of the calibration pipeline will rely on off-the-shelf tools available via the Common Astronomy Software Applications (CASA). The latter provides the necessary functionality to implement all logical functions (including self-calibration) required for end-to-end calibration of ARGOS data. The pipeline can rely on existing, well-tested end-to-end implementations such as the IDIA PROCESSMEERKAT framework developed for MeerKAT (Collier, et al. 2021). This framework demonstrates good scalability, making dynamic use of resources and containers.

3.2 Physical design of the pulsar pipeline

Most logical functions of the pulsar timing pipeline can be implemented using established public software libraries and file formats. The proposed logical-to-physical functional mapping is as follows:

- The *coherent de-dispersion* and *folding* logical functions shall be implemented using `dspr`, an open-source C++/cuda library for digital signal processing of pulsar astronomical timeseries. `Dspr` provides efficient GPU implementations of de-dispersion and filtebank formation algorithms. The folding algorithm requires a polynomial predictor for the pulsar rotational phase. The latter shall be generated using `tempo2`, an open-source pulsar timing package.
- *RFI excision* shall be implemented using `psrchive` (van Strater, et al. 2011), in particular using `psrchive::paz`.
- *Polarisation* and *flux calibration* functions shall be implemented using `psrchive::pac` and `psrchive::pcm` which can also apply the Measurement Equation Modelling (MEM) and Measuring

Equation Template Matching (METM) methods to calibrate the cross-coupling terms of the receiver response.

- For the times-of-arrival logical function, we plan to test two independent implementations: one based on `psrchive::pam` and `psrchive::pat` to perform template matching on frequency-averaged 1D profiles, and one that implements a 2D template matching algorithm (e.g. (Liu 2014)). The former shall be implemented as part of the standard pipeline, while the latter shall be available on demand.
- The dynamic spectra logical function shall be implemented using `dspsr`.
- The database logical function will be implemented using existing frameworks such as `toaster/coastguard` that is currently used for Effelsberg timing experiments.
- Diagnostics and plots shall be produced using `psrchive::pav` and `psrchive::psrstat`.
- For the timing logical function, we shall also test two independent implementations, one based on the TEMPO2 timing package, and one based on `pint`.
- The outlier and transient detection logical function shall be realized by a yet-to-be implemented library using state-of-the art machine learning and unsupervised classification schemes.

3.3 Physical design of the imaging pipeline

The imaging pipeline is written predominantly in functional Python² following community standards for best practices. Standard 3rd-party packages, such as `numpy`, `scipy`, `astropy`, `matplotlib`, etc. are not explicitly mentioned but are expected to be employed.

- Metadata and building commands will be provided in `pyproject.toml` configuration files. This will include all the required dependencies with minimum versions.
- Where appropriate, unit tests will be written to test the basic components of the software and `pytest`³ will be used to execute and record the test results.
- Continuous integration tests will be triggered automatically via GitHub Actions⁴.
- Application programming interface (API) documentation will be included via `docstrings` for every module, class and function in the code. This documentation will be rendered as user-friendly HTML using `Sphinx`⁵.
- `Black`⁶ will be used to ensure a consistent coding style.
- `Conda`⁷ `environment.yml` files will be provided for all packages, such that consistent Conda environments can be built for testing.
- Docker images will be deployed on GitHub to allow everyone to run the software without any issues related to package version etc.

The core Python package includes a standard implementation of the Högbom's CLEAN algorithm (Högbom 1974), which has been validated against the Common Astronomy Software Applications⁸ package.

The package contains various routines for simulating the expected input visibilities of the imaging pipelines. These tools will be used to simulate data from both the ARGOS-CDS and the full ARGOS array for testing and benchmarking the image reconstruction tools. This will be particularly useful for evaluating the performance of alternative methods that may be suited to ARGOS than CLEAN, especially considering the computational cost constraints.

² <https://www.python.org>

³ <https://docs.pytest.org>

⁴ <https://docs.github.com/en/actions>

⁵ <https://www.sphinx-doc.org>

⁶ <https://black.readthedocs.io>

⁷ <https://conda.io>

⁸ <https://casa.nrao.edu>

Machine learning methods will be implemented using either TensorFlow⁹ and/or JAX¹⁰. Iterative proximal optimisation methods will make use of PySAP¹¹ (Farrens, et al. 2020), which includes the modular optimisation library, ModOpt¹², and the wavelet and sparsity package, Sparse2D¹³. All computationally expensive network training and testing will be carried out on the IDRIS Jean Zay¹⁴ GPU cluster. Less intensive training and data production can be carried out at onsite ARGOS facilities.

3.4 Physical design of the transient search pipeline

The transient search capability is integrated into the Effelsberg Direct Digitisation backend. The new capabilities are written into the XLibs¹⁵ and TransientX¹⁶ softwares, and a simple FFT spectrometer/integrator is built on top of the new DADAFLOW framework in PSRDADA_CPP¹⁷. Currently, the input of the pipeline is the un-channelised raw voltage, and will be updated to be the FP32 filterbank data for ARGOS. The output are PNG files and PSRCHIVE .ar files that contain time and frequency resolved total intensities.

4 Subsystem Compliance Matrix

This section provides the L1 requirements for the Signal-Processing subsystem and how these relate to the L0 requirements for the ARGOS project described in the D2.1: *ARGOS Level 0 Science Requirements (J. Antoniadis 2024)* document. The requirements are listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Mapping to L1 requirements

L1 Requirement ID	Description	Parents	Design
REQ-ARGOS-SP-01	The ARGOS Signal Processing Subsystem shall provide a pipeline that processes raw visibilities, applies a calibration solution and astrometric solution and produces science-ready images	L0_15	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A imaging pipeline that produces reconstructed images from visibilities shall be implemented. The pipeline shall include a calibration process to produce an astrometric solution.
REQ-ARGOS-SP-02	The ARGOS Signal Processing Subsystem shall provide a pulsar processing pipeline that coherently de-disperses the phased-array beam to undo the effects of the interstellar medium, folds the data using the known pulsar ephemerides and produces cadenced time-of-arrival measurements by cross-correlating the pulsar	L0_15	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A pulsar timing pipeline shall be implemented. The pipeline shall provide TOA estimate.

⁹ <https://www.tensorflow.org>

¹⁰ <https://jax.readthedocs.io>

¹¹ <https://github.com/CEA-COSMIC/pysap>

¹² <https://github.com/CEA-COSMIC/ModOpt>

¹³ <https://github.com/CosmoStat/Sparse2D>

¹⁴ <http://www.idris.fr/jean-zay>, 20 000 GPU hours have already been allocated to ARGOS for 2024.

¹⁵ <https://github.com/ypmen/XLibs>

¹⁶ <https://github.com/ypmen/TransientX>

¹⁷ https://gitlab.mpcdf.mpg.de/mpifr-bdg/psrdada_cpp

	time series with pulse template profiles		
REQ-ARGOS-SP-03	The ARGOS Signal Processing Subsystem shall provide a fast radio burst detection and localization pipeline that performs incoherent de-dispersion trials on an incoherent beam and then searches the resulting data stream for bursts	L0_15	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A transient pipeline shall be implemented. • The pipeline shall be capable of localize the bursts and send real time alerts.
REQ-ARGOS-SP-04	The ARGOS Signal Processing Subsystem pulsar processing pipeline shall be capable of flagging statistically significant pulse profile changes with respect to a reference profile	L0_25	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The pulsar pipeline shall be capable of computing the significance of detection at the level of the profile.
REQ-ARGOS-SP-05	The ARGOS Signal Processing Subsystem pulsar processing pipeline shall be capable of updating timing ephemerides for pulsar targets with a cadence of less than 24 hours	L0_26	
REQ-ARGOS-SP-06	The ARGOS Signal Processing Subsystem pulsar processing pipeline shall be capable of providing alerts for glitches, strong scattering events, and other timing irregularities for all its pulsar targets	L0_27	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The pulsar pipeline shall be capable of providing real time alerts when a detection is notified.
REQ-ARGOS-SP-07	The ARGOS Signal Processing Subsystem imaging processing pipeline shall not degrade the absolute photometric accuracy of image-domain products below 5%	L0_31	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The imaging pipeline shall not degrade the photometry to more than 5%. Benchmarking of different methods is mandatory.
REQ-ARGOS-SP-08	The ARGOS Signal Processing Subsystem imaging processing pipeline shall not degrade the absolute astrometric accuracy of image-domain products by more than 10% of the FWHM of the synthesised beam	L0_32	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The imaging pipeline shall not degrade the astrometry to more than 10% of the FWHM of the beam. The calibration of the astrometry shall be tested carefully with known sources or simulated data.
REQ-ARGOS-SP-09	The ARGOS Signal Processing Subsystem imaging processing pipeline shall provide	L0_38	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The imaging pipeline shall detect the sources and provide real time alerts for significant detection.

	real-time detections and astrometric positions for all point sources detected with a significance greater than 10 sigma		
REQ-ARGOS-SP-10	The ARGOS Signal Processing Subsystem transient processing pipeline shall trigger low-latency (<1 min) alerts for time-domain transients with flux, DM, polarisation and positional information	L0_43	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The transient pipeline shall compute the flux, DM, polarisation and position of the source and provide real time alerts containing these informations.
REQ-ARGOS-SP-11	The ARGOS Signal Processing Subsystem transient processing pipeline shall be capable of offline processing of channelized voltage data	L0_44	

5 Overall architecture

This section provides diagrams depicting the flow of data in and out of the various Signal-Processing subsystem pipelines and how they interface with other ARGOS subsystems.

Figure 13: Diagram of the ARGOS imaging pipeline.

Figure 14: Pulsar processing pipeline.

Figure 15: FRB detection and localisation pipeline.

6 Results & actualization

6.1 Results

This subsection details the results obtained with the ARGOS Signal-Processing subsystem at time of writing.

6.1.1 Image reconstruction pipeline

To demonstrate the results of the image reconstruction pipeline using the CLEAN algorithm, we first use the ARGOS-CDS setup. Figure 16 shows the positions of the five ARGOS-CDS antennas, along with the corresponding baselines and the uv-plane coverage. The uv-plane assumes a single frequency sample at 2

GHz and observations taken over multiple time steps (24 time steps of 300 seconds each) for a total of two hours of observation. The array is positioned at the latitude of Heraklion, with the source at a declination of 90° . The starting hour angle is set to -30 minutes.

Figure 16: Array configuration for ARGOS-CDS. Left panel: positions of the five antennas. Middle panel: baselines associated to the array configuration. Right panel: associated uv-plane.

Figure 17 shows an example of the integrated CLEAN implementation within the imaging pipeline applied to a set of simulated point sources. The reconstructed image clearly recovers the ground truth point sources as expected, however, residual artifacts are visible. These artifacts could potentially be mitigated upon using more sophisticated image processing and machine learning tools.

Figure 17: Example of the CLEAN algorithm applied to simulated point sources. Left panel: ground truth sky model of the simulated point sources. Middle panel: dirty observation of the simulated point sources, for a single band observation. Right panel: reconstructed observations after running the CLEAN algorithm.

Figure 18 shows an example of a multiband observation, simulated with 128 frequency samples spanning the range from 1 to 3 GHz over a two hours period. This serves as a basic demonstration of the tools that will be used for validating the performance of the image reconstruction tools.

Figure 18: Example of multiband observation. Left panel: ground truth sky model of the simulated point sources. Middle panel: dirty observation of the simulated point sources, for a multiband observation. Right panel: associated dirty observation of the simulated point sources for the observation at 2 GHz.

We also investigate the array configuration and observation for the full ARGOS array. Figure 19 shows the position of the potential positions of the antennas for ARGOS: 176 antennas randomly distributed and 1024 antennas arranged on a regular grid. The figure also shows the corresponding baselines and uv-plane, calculated assuming a single frequency sample at 2 GHz and observations conducted over multiple time steps (6 time steps of 5 minutes each) for a total of 30 minutes. The arrays are positioned at the latitude of Heraklion, with the source at a declination of 90° . The starting hour angle is set to -30 minutes.

Figure 19: Array configuration for full ARGOS. Left panel: position of the five antennas. Middle panel: baselines associated to the array configuration. Right panel: associated uv-plane.

Figure 20 shows an example of running the integrated CLEAN implementation on the same set of simulated point sources. The reconstruction clearly recovers the ground truth point sources as expected, with less residual artifacts than ARGOS-CDS.

Figure 20: Example of the CLEAN algorithm applied to simulated point sources. Left panel: ground truth sky model of the simulated point sources. Middle panel: dirty observation of the simulated point sources, for a single band observation. Right panel: reconstructed observations after running the CLEAN algorithm.

Finally, Figure 21 shows an example of a multiband observation, simulated with 11 frequency samples spanning the range from 1 to 3 GHz over a 30 minutes period. The observations show less artifact than the one realized with the ARGOS-CDS setup.

Figure 21: Example of multiband observation. Left panel: Ground truth sky model of the simulated point sources. Middle panel: Dirty observation of the simulated point sources, for a multiband observation. Right panel: Associated dirty observation of the simulated point sources for the observation at 2 GHz.

We performed a preliminary estimate of the computation time required to run the CLEAN algorithm on the single band visibilities, using the Docker provided in the argosim package. For the ARGOS-CDS forecast, the image size is 512^2 pixels and the CLEAN algorithm produces a result in approximately 0.09 seconds. For the full ARGOS array, with an image of 4096^2 pixels, the computation time increases to approximately 9.45 seconds. This initial estimate suggests that the computational time for CLEAN scales with the number of pixels in the image. However, this preliminary study should not be considered as a definitive reference, as the complexity of the sky model or the number of sources can influence the simulated visibilities, and thus the computational time. Once additional methods are developed, we will conduct a more detail benchmark analysis.

The most significant results obtained so far regarding image reconstruction are presented in (Chiche, et al. 2023). This paper details two novel machine learning architectures (2D-1D Net and Deflation Net) that have been used to reconstruct 3D (2D spatial + 1D temporal) radio imaging data and identify transient sources. Both methods are shown to outperform CLEAN at reconstructing simulated data cubes. Figure 22 shows the pixel reconstruction performance as function of noise level of the two networks with respect to the CLEAN algorithm. Please refer to the paper for a comprehensive description of the methodology and results on simulated radio data. Further results, including the use of this method, will be provided for simulated ARGOS data following the tagging of v1.0 of the pipeline.

Figure 22: $\log(\text{RMSE}_{\text{noise}})$ averaged over the test cubes at different values of σ_ϵ . The vertical bars show the standard deviation. Because of the log scale, the standard deviation is higher when $\text{RMSE}_{\text{noise}}$ is small. This is the case for the DL-based methods (Chiche, et al. 2023).

6.2 Deployment Plan

All of the Signal-Processing subsystem software will be made publicly available and fully open-source via the official ARGOS GitHub Organisation¹⁸. Each of the pipelines described in this document will have a dedicated repository where the code can be maintained, versioned and tagged for specific releases. Each repository will include automatically generated API documentation and an automatically generated Docker¹⁹ image with the versioned software pre-installed. These images will not only ease installation of the software on various platforms, but also guarantee (as much as is possible) the reproducibility of the results obtained from a given pipeline on a specific dataset. Each repository will also contain a `README.md` file with quick-start information on how to install and run the software.

If needed/appropriate, additional repositories containing common ARGOS data management/processing tools can also be made available on GitHub. These packages could also be deployed on platforms such as the Python Package Index²⁰ or Anaconda²¹ for ease of use within ARGOS packages and for the wider community.

6.3 Upgrade Plan

All Signal-Processing subsystem software will adhere to the following release and upgrade plan.

- An initial version (v1.0) for every package will be tagged following tests on simulated ARGOS data.
- Follow-up patches (e.g. v1.0.1 etc.), minor releases (e.g. v1.1 etc.), and major releases (e.g. v2.0) will be made to fix bugs, add new features and (if needed) adapt to changes in the simulated or real data releases.
- For the relevant pipelines, ARGOS-CDS-specific versions can be tagged for processing the real CDS data. Every CDS data release will be tied to specific pipeline versions to ensure reproducibility.
- The same process will be adopted for processing data releases from the full ARGOS array for all of the pipelines.

¹⁸ <https://github.com/ARGOS-telescope>

¹⁹ <https://www.docker.com>

²⁰ <https://pypi.org>

²¹ <https://anaconda.org>

7 Conclusions

This document has summarised the planned design and initial results obtained for the ARGOS Signal-Processing subsystem.

Significant progress has been made in the development of the imaging pipeline, which will provide 2D and 3D image reconstruction of ARGOS data, as well as detection of transient sources. Follow-up versions of the document will provide further details of the remaining pipelines.

A key aspect of the validation of these tools will be a comprehensive set of simulated ARGOS data, for both the full array as well as the ARGOS-CDS. This will enable thorough performance, scalability and interface testing. This will also make it possible to set benchmarks for comparing different algorithms in order to select the tools best suited to the ARGOS science cases.

8 References

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